

Posterior cerebral artery stroke presenting with acute onset psychosis in an elderly woman

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ABSTRACT:

Psychiatric illness, acute or subacute, may be an indicator of neurological disorders, particularly a stroke or tumor in the occipital and or temporal cortex.

Posterior cerebral artery (PCA) territory stroke is a common and important neurological illness masquerading an acute or subacute onset psychosis in the form of visual hallucinations, particularly in elderly people with vascular risk factors.

We depict here a patient with acute onset psychosis presenting with visual hallucinations and aggressive behavior without any previous history of psychosis in a 76 yr. old hypertensive and diabetic woman whose illness was eventually attributed to a subacute ischemic infarct in her distal right PCA territory.

Being aware of the visual hallucinations, she showed anxious and aggressive behavior. An immediate MRI brain was done which revealed subacute infarct in distal right PCA territory - the occipital (striate and peristriate) cortex with a central area of hemosiderin deposition. Reassurance and modest doses of antipsychotic drug with statin, antihypertensive and oral hypoglycemic agent (OHA) resulted in gradual amelioration of her symptoms.

Keywords: Psychiatric illness, neurological disorders,

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INTRODUCTION:

One of the important causes of psychosis as presenting manifestation of a neurological disease is stroke in the posterior cerebral artery (PCA) territory.

We depict here a 76 yr. old woman who developed visual hallucinations of sudden onset while traveling to a remote hill station with her daughter. Apparently her insight was normal as she was aware of her hallucinations. An MR brain image showed scattered areas of ischemic infarct in her right distal PCA territory, the occipital cortex with subtle hemorrhagic conversion. Conservative treatment with rest, assurance and statin, antihypertensive, OHA with a second generation antipsychotic drug quetiapin resulted in modest recovery of her symptoms.

CASE PRESENTATION:

The patient was traveling to a hill station 1 day ago with her daughter where, as alleged by her daughter, she suddenly developed seeing unfamiliar faces and moving figures around her without having any visual blurring. She was however aware of her visual hallucinations which made her scary enough to be aggressive with emotional outburst off and on.

She was a diabetic, hypertensive elderly woman who was being treated for sensory polyneuropathy for which she had a fall about 2 month ago causing fracture of right triquetral bone of wrist, which she could not recall.

She could not clearly recognize the faces of her daughter and son-in-law (prosopagnosia), and had to rely on their voice for identification. Aphasia, and alexia were absent with normal naming and fluency. There was no achromatopsia and her color recognition as well as object identification was normal. Her recent memory domain was impaired as she developed forgetfulness of recent events.

On examination, her blood pressure was 180/90, though she denied having high blood pressure earlier.

Confrontation test for her visual field assessment revealed left homonymous hemianopia. There was inadequacy in her recall of recent memory.

MRI brain DW image (fig. 1) showed nonhomogeneous hyperintensity in and around the calcarine cortex (parasagittal and retrotrigonal areas) with T2 (fig. 2) and flair (fig. 3) hyperintensity consistent with subacute ischemic infarct. There was a central blooming hypointensity in gradient echo image (fig. 4) indicating eventual hemorrhagic conversion. The T2 flair image (fig. 4) also showed periventricular leukoaraiosis, characteristic of diffuse cerebral small vessel disease. Basal ganglia showed normal attenuation. There was normal flow voids in the vertebro-basilar and proximal PCA circulation. Her fasting and postprandial blood sugar were 186 and 256 mg/dl respectively indicating an uncontrolled state of diabetes mellitus.

She was managed with assurance, statin, antihypertensive, OHA and a second generation antipsychotic, quetiapin in modest doses for about 3 weeks which resulted in substantial improvement of her psychosis. Her statin, OHA and antihypertensive therapy was continued and antipsychotic drug was gradually withdrawn in following 6 wks. Follow up at next 3 and 6 months after withdrawal of antipsychotic drug showed absence of visual hallucinations and normal visual recognition of faces.

Figure legend:

MRI brain:

fig. 1. DW image showing patchy hyperintensity in right occipital cortex.

fig. 2. T2W image showing hyperintensity in parasagittal calcarine cortex.

fig 3. Flair image showing hyperintensity in occipital as well as periventricular regions consistent with subacute ischemic infarct with leukoaraiosis.

Fig. 4: Gradient eco image showing a central blooming hypointensity indicating low grade hemorrhagic conversion.

DISCUSSION:

Acute or subacute onset psychosis with visual hallucinations may be presenting symptoms of a number of neurological diseases like stroke or tumor in the occipital cortex (1, 2, and 3). Bilateral posterior cerebral artery stroke often produce anosognosia with cortical blindness (4).

The history here is of a 76 yr. old woman who developed visual hallucinations of sudden onset. She was traveling to a hill station a week ago with her daughter where, as alleged by her daughter, she suddenly developed psychosis in the form of visual hallucinations.

She was however aware of her visual hallucinations since there was no significant damage to the peristriate association area (5). However, the visual hallucination and improper face recognition made her scary enough to be aggressive with emotional outburst off and on. This symptom, characteristic of prosopagnosia with relatively normal insight, is a distinctive feature of occipital cortex stroke, particularly of right side (5). Her MRI brain revealed subacute infarct in right occipital (the striate and peristriate) cortex corresponding to a distal PCA (P4, cortical) territory with central hemosiderin deposition. There was peri ventricular leukoariosis, a feature of diffuse cerebral small vessel disease, without any abnormal signal in basal ganglia.

She was managed with reassurance, supportive treatment including antidiabetic, antihypertensive, and statin in addition to a second generation antipsychotic drug for 3 weeks. Antiplatelets could not be used as her MRI brain showed subtle hemorrhagic conversion and periventricular leukoariosis. Clopidogrel 75 mg per day was added to her treatment at her follow up after 3 wks, under supervision.

Substantial improvement of her psychosis occurred in about next 6 weeks with gradual disappearance of visual hallucinations. Statin, oral hypoglycemic

agents (OHA), antihypertensive, and supportive treatment were continued and antipsychotic was gradually withdrawn in following 3 months.

CONCLUSION:

Since neurological disease of diverse etiology can mimic acute or subacute onset psychosis initially (6), it is prudent to work up accordingly to detect the specific brain abnormalities in such cases. Treatment should be aimed at alleviating the risk factor like hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes mellitus, with modest doses of antipsychotic medications for an appropriate time period.

Conflict of interest:

There is no conflict of interest in this paper

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